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Power management control in microgrid

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Abstract:

This paper explores the Conventional Droop Control (CDC) strategy for inverter-based distributed generation in microgrids. Through MATLAB/Simulink simulations, the study demonstrates CDC's effectiveness in decentralized real power sharing and frequency regulation. However, challenges in reactive power distribution and voltage regulation due to line impedance differences are identified. The findings highlight CDC's robustness in real power management while suggesting the need for advanced techniques to improve reactive power control and voltage accuracy in microgrids.

Keywords:

Microgrid, Droop Control, Distributed Generation, Power Management, Decentralized Control.

1. Introduction:

In the evolving landscape of modern power systems, the integration of distributed generation (DG) units, particularly inverter-based resources, has become a cornerstone in the development of microgrids. A crucial aspect of ensuring the stability and reliability of these microgrids is the control strategy employed to manage the power output of these DG units. Among the various control methods, the Conventional Droop Control (CDC) strategy stands out due to its simplicity and effectiveness in facilitating decentralized power sharing among inverters.

The fundamental principle of CDC is grounded in the balance between input mechanical power and output electrical power in synchronous generators. Variations in this balance lead to changes in generator rotor speed, which in turn affect the system frequency. By mimicking this behavior, inverters under CDC adjust their output frequency and voltage magnitude in response to real and reactive power demands, respectively. This self-regulating mechanism ensures that power is shared proportionally among inverters based on their capacity, thereby maintaining the overall power balance within the microgrid.

This paper presents a detailed analysis of the CDC strategy, supported by simulations conducted using MATLAB/Simulink. The study explores the power sharing dynamics of parallel inverters, with a particular focus on the distribution of real and reactive power, as well as the corresponding frequency and voltage responses. Through these simulations, the paper highlights the effectiveness of CDC in achieving accurate real power distribution and frequency regulation. However, it also addresses the challenges associated with reactive power sharing and voltage regulation, particularly in the presence of line impedance differences between inverters.

The organization of the paper is as follows: Section 2 delves into the theoretical foundation of CDC, outlining the key equations that govern the droop characteristics. Section 3 provides a comprehensive overview of the simulation setup, including the parameters used and the block diagram of the CDC implementation. The results of the simulations are presented offering insights into the performance of CDC under various operating conditions. Finally, the paper concludes with a discussion on the implications of the findings.

2. Conventional droop control (CDC):

The underlying principle of CDC is to mimic the behavior of conventional synchronous generators, allowing inverters to share load dynamically and proportionally without centralized communication. CDC is widely used and documented in literature.

The basic operating principle of droop-based methods is balance of input and output power of synchronous generators in power grid. The input to synchronous generator is mechanical power (P_m) and output is electrical power (P_e). When $P_m > P_e$, the generator rotor accelerates, causing rise in the frequency and vice versa. Similarly, output reactive power fluctuations cause voltage magnitude deviations. In essence, this approach leverages the fundamental relationship between the flow of real and reactive power per phase across two nodes connected by a line impedance as

$$P_i = \frac{1}{Z_i} [(V_i V_0 \cos [\delta_i - \theta_i] - V_0^2) \cos [\theta_i] + V_i V_0 \sin [\delta_i] \sin [\theta_i]] \quad (1)$$

$$Q_i = \frac{1}{Z_i} [(V_i V_0 \cos [\delta_i - \theta_i] - V_0^2) \sin [\theta_i] + V_i V_0 \sin [\delta_i] \cos [\theta_i]] \quad (2)$$

where δ and θ are phase and impedance angles, respectively. The voltage at PCC, inverter output voltage and impedance magnitude are denoted by V_0, V_i and Z_i , respectively. In inductive lines, real part of Z can be neglected. In practical systems, the phase difference $[\delta]_i$ between bus voltages is small leading to $\cos [\delta_i] = 1$ and, $\sin [\delta_i] = \delta_i$. Hence power transfer equations in (1) and (2) can be simplified to (3) and (4).

$$P_i = (V_i V_0) / X_i \delta_i \quad (3)$$

$$Q_i = V_0 / X_i (V_i - V_0) \quad (4)$$

As indicated by equations (3) and (4), the generation of reactive power is directly tied with the difference in voltage magnitude, and the real power output from the DG unit is entirely based upon the phase angle difference.

Figure. 1: Typical droop characteristics of conventional droop control

Fig. 1 illustrates this behavior, where the relationship between the real power output (P_i) of the i^{th} inverter and the frequency (ω) can be expressed as:

$$\omega_i - \omega^* = -SP_{P_i}(P_i - P_i^*) \quad (5)$$

$$SP_{P_i} = \frac{\Delta\omega}{P_{imax}} = \frac{f_{max} - f_{min}}{P_{imax}} \quad (6)$$

In this equation, P_i represents the actual real power output of the i^{th} inverter, P_{imax} denotes the maximum real power capacity of the i^{th} DG inverter, ω_{min} signifies the minimum permissible operating frequency, and SP_{P_i} is the slope of the droop characteristic curve and termed as droop coefficient.

Initially, during grid-connected operation, each inverter-based DG unit is engineered to deliver a predetermined real power output (P_i) at the standardized base frequency (ω). This base frequency is maintained by the robust utility grid.

Upon transitioning to islanded mode, the power outputs of each inverter must swiftly adapt, adhering to their specific droop characteristics. This adaptation is crucial to ensure that the collective power generated by the DG units aligns with the demand of critical loads within the MG. This dynamic response allows the MG to establish a new equilibrium at a modified steady-state frequency (ω).

Following a similar principle, the magnitude setpoint of each DG's output voltage can be adjusted based on a designated Q–E droop scheme to manage the reactive power flow within the MG. This relationship can be mathematically represented as follows:

$$V_i - V^* = -SP_{Q_i}(Q_i - Q_i^*) \quad (7)$$

$$SP_{Q_i} = \frac{\Delta V}{Q_{imax}} = \frac{V_{max} - V_{min}}{Q_{imax}} \quad (8)$$

The reactive power output (Q_i) of the i^{th} DG is governed by a Q-V droop mechanism, where it's adjusted in relation to the voltage magnitude ($|V|$) compared to a minimum threshold ($|V_{\min}|$). In this relationship, Q_{\max} represents the maximum reactive power capacity of the i^{th} DG, and SP_{Q_i} (negative) is the slope of the droop characteristic curve. When the MG is connected to the main grid, the dispatched reactive power of the i^{th} DG unit is denoted as Q_i , and the corresponding voltage magnitude at the point of common coupling (PCC) is V .

Fig. 1 illustrates the ideal scenario of reactive power sharing among DG units utilizing voltage droop control.

The droop coefficients, SP_{P_i} & SP_{Q_i} , must be adjusted inversely proportional to their power ratings to ensure load power demand is shared proportionally to their respective capacities. Equations (9) and (10) illustrate this relation

$$SP_{P_1} \cdot P_1 = SP_{P_2} \cdot P_2 = \dots = SP_{P_i} \cdot P_i \quad (9)$$

$$SP_{Q_1} \cdot Q_1 = SP_{Q_2} \cdot Q_2 = \dots = SP_{Q_i} \cdot Q_i \quad (10)$$

Fig. 2 depicts the graphical representation of CDC method. The microgrid is synchronized with the main grid using a droop control. The block diagram of the droop control is shown in the Fig. 3. The main blocks as seen are the power droop control and the voltage and current loop control.

The voltage and current output of the DG inverter module are sensed. This is followed by calculating the output power that is processed through a low pass filter and power calculating unit.

The differential power is the difference between measured DG inverter output power and rated power of DG. The product of differential power and P-f droop coefficient is subtracted from rated nominal voltage to obtain the reference voltage.

In continuation, in order to control the injection of the reactive power, the nominal reactive power (Q_N) and measured reactive power Q are sensed and difference is calculated and this is multiplied by the Q-V droop coefficient D_Q that is compared with the nominal voltage V^* to finally calculate the reference voltage (V).

Figure. 2: Block diagram of droop control strategy

3. Simulation and results:

This section presents analysis of conventional droop control strategy. This is executed through extensive simulations using MATLAB/Simulink as per the circuit diagram shown in Fig. 3. The controller simulation parameters are provided in Table. I.

Figure. 1: Microgrid model used for simulation

Table. 1: Simulation parameters

	Parameter	Value
Inverter Filter	R_f	0.1Ω

	L_f	2.5mH
	C_f	50 μ F
Line Parameters	$R_{L1} + jX_{L1}$	0.1+ j0.2356 Ω
	$R_{L2} + jX_{L2}$	0.12 + j0.1571 Ω
System Parameters	Frequency (f)	50Hz
	Voltage	240V
Load 1	P+jQ kVA	40+j30 kVA
Load 2	P+jQ kVA	40+j30 kVA
CDC	D_p	1.57x 10 ⁻⁵ rad/W.s
	D_Q	2x10 ⁻⁴ V/VAr

Figure. 4: Real power distribution among parallel inverters in cdc

Figure. 5: Reactive power distribution among parallel inverters in cdc

Figure. 6: Frequency response in CDC

Figure. 7: Voltage outputs in parallel inverters in CDC

Fig. 4 and 5 depict the real and reactive power outputs of parallel inverters. Fig. 6 and 7 depict the frequency response and voltage response of equal capacity parallel inverters when subjected to the load. It can be seen the real power distribution and frequency response is accurate, but the reactive power sharing and output voltages of parallel inverters become inaccurate because of line impedance mismatches.

As seen above, the CDC technique allows the operation of DG inverters without the need for them to communicate with one another, which enhances their reliability. However, this method does come with several limitations, including:

3.1. Inaccurate power sharing:

Variations in the impedance of transmission lines connecting the parallel inverters can cause unequal voltage drops and circulating reactive currents. This results in different power outputs from DG units intended to share load equally, affecting the accuracy of power sharing.

For a narrow range of frequency deviations, a small droop coefficient is necessary, which compromises active power sharing. However, increasing the droop coefficient enhances active power sharing but at the cost of greater voltage deviations from nominal values.

3.2. Frequency and voltage excursions:

Some RES integrated through inverters have low or no inertia, affecting the system's ability to stabilize frequency quickly

When operating in islanding mode, CDC adjusts the output of DG units based on changes in load without direct communication between units. While a sharper droop curve can improve load distribution, it may also lead to significant deviations in frequency and voltage, potentially destabilizing the MG. This underscores the fundamental compromise between achieving precise load sharing and maintaining frequency and voltage stability inherent to the droop approach.

3.3. Impact of harmonic loads:

CDC is designed primarily for power sharing of fundamental components of powers and fails to address the sharing of harmonic power in the presence of nonlinear loads. Additionally, in harmonic environment the process of computing and conditioning active and reactive power introduces delays, leading to a sluggish dynamic response. Inadequate harmonic management can result in degraded power quality.

Intermittent output from renewable sources: The original droop method struggles with RES based DGs due to the irregular and unpredictable nature of the output power from these micro-sources, further challenging the method's effectiveness.

The limitations of CDC are well-documented across numerous studies, as indicated by various sources in the literature

4. Conclusion:

This paper has presented an in-depth analysis of the Conventional Droop Control (CDC) strategy, a widely used method for managing the operation of inverter-based distributed generation (DG) units in microgrids. Through both theoretical exploration and extensive simulations using MATLAB/Simulink, the study has demonstrated the efficacy of CDC in enabling decentralized load sharing among parallel inverters without the need for centralized communication.

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